

Docker - Continuous Build Security Assessment

Rocco Gagliardi

Defense Department, scip AG
roga@scip.ch
<https://www.scip.ch>

Marc Ruef (Editor)

Research Department, scip AG
maru@scip.ch
<https://www.scip.ch>

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1. Preface

This paper was written in 2017 as part of a research project at scip AG, Switzerland. It was initially published online at <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20170504> and is available in English and German. Providing our clients with innovative research for the information technology of the future is an essential part of our company culture.

2. Introduction

Docker: “Build, Ship, and Run ...”, *Continuously* is implied. But the jump from *Build* to *Ship* looks pretty simple. Sure, at Docker they know it’s not so simple: before you can ship a container, some tests must be performed.

Docker – in general *containerized software* – claim to optimize the *Continuous-Delivery/-Integration process* (CD/CI), reducing deployment risks, managing the infrastructure as one additional piece of code (*Infrastructure as Software*).

To achieve the *Continuous Delivery* (CD) – where you build software that can be released to production at any time – you need a *Continuous-Integration* (CI) process – integrating, building, and testing code within the development environment – and a *Deployment Pipeline* (DP) – every change goes through the pipeline and is automatically applied into production, resulting in many deployments per day. *Continuous Delivery* (CI) just means that you are *able to do frequent deployments* but you may choose *not to do it*, usually because businesses stability.

With particular regard to Docker, what should be tested? Where? How? In this article we try to sketch a test strategy and list some tools.

3. Some Docker terms

Let’s briefly recall some Docker’s ecosystem terms:

- **Docker Host:** Runs the Docker daemon, which does the heavy lifting of building, running, and distributing your Docker containers.
- **Docker File:** A Docker file is a text document that contains all the commands you would normally execute manually in order to build a Docker image. Docker can build images automatically by reading the instructions from a Docker File.

- **Docker Image:** Docker images are the basis of containers. An Image is an ordered collection of root filesystem changes and the corresponding execution parameters for use within a container runtime. An image typically contains a union of layered filesystems stacked on top of each other. An image does not have state and it never changes.
- **Docker Container:** A container is a runtime instance of a Docker image. A Docker container consists of a Docker image, an Execution environment, a standard set of instructions.

4. Test Strategy

Once the main components of the Docker-family has been identified, we can think about how and where to perform some security tests.

The following table sketches our testing strategy:

Test Area	Goal	Tests	When
Docker Host	Assure the host running Docker process has been secured following best practices.	Is the OS updated? Is the OS hardened? (CIS Benchmark) Is the OS exposure minimized?	Integrate the results, no strictly correlated with the CI cycle.
Docker File	Assure the container’s definition follows best practices.	Is the source trusted? (FROM:) Is the environment minimized? (RUN ...) Is the network exposure minimized? (EXPOSE) Is the volume exposure minimized? (VOLUME)	Integrated in the CI cycle.

Docker Image	Assure the image's static safety.	Is the image trusted? The image has known vulnerabilities?	Integrated in the CI cycle.
Docker Container	Assure the image's dynamic safety.	The container has known vulnerabilities? The container network exposure is minimized as in the Docker file? The container volume exposure is minimized as in the Docker file?	Integrated in the CI cycle.

5. Test Tools

In order to be *Continuous*, all the tests must be integrated in the different pipelines: no manual intervention should be required.

Following is a list of tools to look for:

Tool	Test Area	Method	License
<i>docker-bench-security</i> [1]	Docker Host	Runs the script in a container to obtain a report. Checks are based on the CIS Docker 1.6 Benchmark.	Apache 2.0
<i>OpenSCAP</i> [2]	Docker Images + Docker Container	Use the oscap-docker to scan images/container against the CVE or custom policy and get the report.	GPLv3
<i>Clair</i> [3]	Docker Images + Docker Container	Clair is an open source project for the static analysis of vulnerabilities in application containers. Used mostly via API, the tool get vulnerability from different sources, scans the images for the installed packages, and reports threats found. Clair is part of the CoreOS products family.	Apache 2.0

<i>Twistlock</i> [4]	Docker Images Docker Container Packages	Uses NIST to find CVEs and the Docker CIS for vulnerability assessment. Runtime defense (a specialized container deployed on each Docker Host) allows security monitoring and reaction.	Commercial
<i>Aqua Security</i> [5]	Docker Images + Docker Container + Packages	It works pretty much in the same way as Twistlock does, using a central server and agent containers running in privileged mode on every Docker host. Scalock provides a comprehensive security solution for virtual containers by adding visibility and control to containerized environments, enabling organizations to scale-out without security limitations even on a very large scale.	Commercial

6. Summary

Docker's ecosystem is relative new and changing rapidly. Testing is just a small part of the big picture; many other factors must be considered in order to choose the right tool. The testing methodology and objective are clear; the integration in the CD/CI process depends on the customer's architecture.

7. External Links

[1] <https://github.com/docker/docker-bench-security>

[2] <https://www.open-scap.org/>

[3] <https://github.com/coreos/clair>

[4] <https://www.twistlock.com/>

[5] <https://www.aquasec.com/>

